

EFFECTIVENESS OF ENDOSCOPIC POSTERIOR NASAL NEURECTOMY FOR ALLERGIC RHINITIS

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Abstract:

Background:

Allergic, vasomotor or non-allergic rhinitis and mixed types are all subdivisions of Chronic Rhinitis (CR). CR can dramatically impair the quality of life in a patient with long standing symptoms as watery rhinorrhea, sneezing, nasal congestion, post nasal drip and itchy nose and eyes. This study aims to assess the outcomes of Posterior Nasal Neurectomy in patients with symptoms of chronic rhinorrhea, nasal congestion, sneezing, and post nasal drip due to refractory Allergic Rhinitis.

Aims and objectives:

To assess the outcomes of Posterior Nasal Neurectomy in patients with symptoms of chronic rhinorrhea, nasal congestion, sneezing, post nasal drip due to refractory Allergic Rhinitis

Methods: This is an interventional study having 40 patients those with symptoms of chronic Allergic or Vasomotor rhinitis at Trichy SRM medical college and hospital. Patients had treatment with nasal decongestants, antihistamines, oral steroids, topical steroidal sprays earlier for 3 months; patients who were not benefited are now evaluated with local examination of nose, Nasal endoscopy, Absolute eosinophilic count, positive skin test etc. Patients were asked for scoring of their symptoms as per Total Nose Symptom Score (TNSS) pre operatively. These patients were subjected for Endoscopic Posterior Nasal Neurectomy and were further evaluated with the same scoring post operatively on day 7, 3 month and on 6 month follow up. Improvement in symptoms and scoring was analyzed.

Results: Mean age of the study participant was 35.70 ± 9.46 years. Regarding symptoms majority of the 33 (82.5%) participants had a complaints of running nose. The mean pre-operative TNSS was 7.98 ± 0.974 , mean TNSS on post-operative day 7 was 6.43 ± 0.931 , mean follow up third month TNSS was 3.10 ± 0.709 and mean follow up sixth month TNSS was 2.83 ± 0.636 . The mean TNSS was significantly decreasing after performing endoscopic posterior nasal neurectomy over different time period.

Conclusion: Endoscopic posterior nasal neurectomy (EPNN) is a treatment for allergic rhinitis, effectively alleviating symptoms like nasal congestion, rhinorrhea, and sneezing by interrupting neural pathways. However, further research is needed to establish EPNN as a standard treatment.

Keywords: *Allergic Rhinitis, Total Nose Symptom Score & endoscopic posterior nasal neurectomy*

INTRODUCTION:

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a widespread chronic inflammatory disorder of the nasal mucosa affecting individuals globally, with varying prevalence rates across different regions. It is characterized by symptoms such as rhinorrhea, nasal congestion, sneezing, and post-nasal drip, leading to significant impairment in quality of life, productivity, and overall well-being. Globally, AR affects approximately 10-30% of the population, with a higher prevalence observed in developed countries compared to developing nations^[1]. In India, the prevalence of AR varies geographically but is estimated to affect around 10-15% of the population, with higher rates reported in urban areas

and among younger age groups^[2]. Despite the availability of various treatment modalities, including pharmacotherapy, immunotherapy, and environmental control measures, a subset of patients with AR experience persistent symptoms refractory to conventional therapies. These individuals often undergo repeated courses of medication, incurring substantial healthcare costs, and may still not achieve adequate symptom control. For this subgroup of patients with refractory AR, there remains an unmet clinical need for alternative therapeutic modalities that offer sustained symptom relief and improve overall outcomes^[3,4].

Endoscopic posterior nasal neurectomy (EPNN) has emerged as a potential surgical intervention for patients with refractory AR. Posterior Nasal Neurectomy(PNN) involves the selective denervation of the posterior nasal mucosa, targeting the branches of the sphenopalatine ganglion, which plays a crucial role in the regulation of nasal secretions and mucosal inflammation. By interrupting the neural pathways responsible for mediating allergic responses, PNN aims to provide symptomatic relief in patients with refractory AR^[5,6].

Several studies, have investigated the effectiveness of PNN in patients with refractory AR. A randomised controlled trial by Hua et al^[7]. (2022) demonstrated significant improvements in nasal symptoms, including rhinorrhea, nasal congestion, and sneezing, following PNN in patients with refractory AR. The study reported a reduction in symptom severity scores and a decrease in the need for rescue medication postoperatively. Additionally, long-term follow-up assessments revealed sustained symptom improvement and a low rate of recurrence, highlighting the potential durability of EPNN outcomes. Similarly, a systematic review conducted by Lee et al^[8]. (2022) evaluated the efficacy of EPNN in patients with intractable AR. The analysis included data from multiple studies and reported a significant reduction in nasal symptom scores and medication usage post-EPNN. Furthermore, the review demonstrated a favorable safety profile of EPNN, with minimal adverse effects reported across studies.

Despite these findings, the evidence regarding the effectiveness and long-term outcomes of PNN in the management of refractory AR is still evolving. Nationally, there is a paucity of data specifically evaluating the outcomes of PNN in Indian populations, including those residing in Tamil Nadu. Understanding the effectiveness of PNN in this demographic subset is crucial due to potential variations in disease prevalence, patient characteristics, and treatment responses^[5,9]. The evaluation of the outcomes of PNN in patients with refractory AR is essential for several reasons. Firstly, it addresses an unmet clinical need by offering an alternative treatment option for patients who have failed to respond adequately to conventional therapies. Secondly, it provides insights into the role of neural modulation in the pathophysiology of AR and its potential as a therapeutic target^[3,10]. Thirdly, it contributes to the optimization of treatment strategies for AR by identifying subgroups of patients who are most likely to benefit from surgical intervention. In summary, assessing the effectiveness of PNN in patients with refractory AR aids advancing our understanding of the condition and optimizing treatment approaches. This study aims to guide clinical decision-making regarding the management of this patient population, specifically within the context of Tamil Nadu, India.

Material and Methods:

It is an Interventional study conducted for a period of 1 year on 40 patients with complaints of long standing Allergic Rhinitis in a tertiary care hospital, Trichy, Tamil Nadu.

Inclusion criteria:

Patients with complaints of long standing watery rhinorrhea, nasal congestion, itchy eyes and nose, sneezing and post nasal drip (refractory to medical treatment)
Age 18 years and above

Exclusion criteria:

Patients with complaints of nasal obstruction and nasal congestion due to deviated nasal septum or other cause of nasal malignancy;.

Study tool: A structured questionnaire was prepared and information was collected about the age of the participant, gender, presenting complaints, examination of ear, Total nasal symptom score (TNSS) which contain the components like nasal congestion, running nose, itching, sneezing and difficulty in sleep. Each components had graded to mild (TNSS score <6), moderate (TNSS score 6 to 9) and severe (TNSS score 9 to 12).

Data collection procedure: After explaining the purpose of the study and obtaining informed written consent from the study participants and information was collected from them. Privacy was ensured through face-to-face interviews conducted by the principal interviewer using pretested structured questionnaires.

Methodology:

This is an interventional study having 40 patients those with symptoms of chronic Allergic or Vasomotor rhinitis at Trichy SRM medical college and hospital. Had treated with nasal decongestions, antihistamines, oral steroids, topical steroidal sprays earlier for 3 months; and who are not benefited are now evaluated with local examination of nose, Nasal endoscopy, Absolute eosinophilic count, positive skin test etc. Patients was asked for scoring of their symptoms as per Total Nose Symptom Score (TNSS) pre operatively. These patients was subjected for Endoscopic Posterior Nasal Neurectomy and was further evaluated with the same scoring post operatively on day 7, 3 month and on 6 month follow up. Improvement in symptoms and scoring was analyzed.

Endoscopic Posterior Nasal Neurectomy procedure:

Under general anesthesia, nasal cavity decongestion was achieved by packing with 1:30,000 adrenaline and adequate decongestion ensured under the middle turbinate. Under endoscopic vision, using zero-degree rigid endoscope, incision given below posterior end of middle turbinate on the lateral wall of nose by using blade, mucosal flap was elevated, the branches of posterior nasal nerve to the middle and inferior turbinates were identified and separated from the sphenopalatine artery, transected and their edges cauterized to prevent accidental re-anastomosis.

Analysis: Data was tabulated in MS Excel and analysed using SPSS version 27.0. All the Continues variables follows normal distribution and were expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD). Categorical variables were expressed as frequency and percentage. Histogram and skewness value (skewness between -0.5 to +0.5: normal distribution) was evaluated to find the normality of quantitative data. Paired sample t test was conducted to assess the mean difference between pre-operative TNSS, post-operative TNSS, follow up third and sixth month TNSS. All the test was two tailed and p value of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Ethical clearance details: Trichy SRM medical college and hospital – Institutional Ethics Committee approved this study on 20/07/2023

Results:**Table 1: Basic characteristics of the study population**

Basic characteristics	Number	Percentage
Age Category		
18 to 30 years	11	27.5%
> 30 to 40 years	21	52.5%
> 40 to 50 years	4	10%
> 50 years	4	10%
Minimum age in years	19	
Maximum age in years	58	
Mean Age \pm SD in years	35.70 \pm 9.46	
Gender		
Male	22	55%
Female	18	45%
Running nose		
Present	33	82.5%
Absent	7	17.5%
Itching		
Present	30	75%
Absent	10	25%
Difficulty in sleeping		
Present	20	50%
Absent	20	50%
Sneezing		
Present	31	77.5%
Absent	9	22.5%
Nasal Congestion		
Present	29	72.5%
Absent	11	27.6%
Previous history of treatment for the same problem		
Present	40	100.0 %
Absent	0	0
Endoscopic Posterior Nasal Neurectomy		
	40	100.0 %
Total	40	100.0 %

Mean age of the study participant was 35.70 \pm 9.46 years. Majority of the participants belongs to the age category of more than 30 to 40 years which is 21 (52.5%) participants. Minimum age observed was 19 years and the maximum age was 58 years. Out of 40 patients, 22 (55%) of them were males and 18 (45%) were females. Regarding

symptoms majority of the 33 (82.5%) participants had a complaints of running nose followed by 31 (77.5%) had sneezing, 30 (75%) had itching over the nose, 29 (72.5%) had nasal congestion and 20 (50%) had difficulty in sleeping. All 40 patients had treatment for the same problem.

Table 2: Comparison between Total Nose Symptom Score in various time period

Total Nose Symptom Score	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	p value
Pre op score	40	7.98	± 0.974	0.154	< 0.001
Post op 7 th day	40	6.43	± 0.931	0.147	
Pre op score	40	7.98	± 0.974	0.154	0.001
Follow up 3 rd month	40	3.10	± 0.709	0.112	
Pre op score	40	7.98	± 0.974	0.154	0.001
Follow up at 6 th month	40	2.83	± 0.636	0.101	
Post op 7 th day	40	6.43	± 0.931	0.147	< 0.001
Follow up 3 rd month	40	3.10	± 0.709	0.112	
Post op 7 th day	40	6.43	± 0.931	0.147	< 0.001
Follow up at 6 th month	40	2.83	± 0.636	0.101	
Follow up 3 rd month	40	3.10	± 0.709	0.112	< 0.001
Follow up at 6 th month	40	2.83	± 0.636	0.101	

Note: p value based on paired sample t test.

The mean pre-operative total nose symptoms score was 7.98 ± 0.974 , mean total nose symptoms score on post-operative day 7 was 6.43 ± 0.931 , mean follow up third month total nose symptoms score was 3.10 ± 0.709 and mean follow up sixth month total nose symptoms score was 2.83 ± 0.636 . Mean pre-operative total nose symptoms score was significantly higher when compared to mean total nose symptoms score on post-operative day 7, on follow up third month and sixth month with the p value shows less than 0.01 respectively. The mean total nose symptoms score was significantly higher among post-operative day 7 when compared to follow up third and sixth month with the p value shows less than 0.01 respectively. The mean total symptoms nose score was significantly higher on follow up third month when compared to follow up sixth month with the p value shows less than 0.01 respectively. The mean total nose symptoms score was significantly decreasing after performing endoscopic posterior nasal neurectomy over different time period.

Figure 1: Line diagram shows Total Nose Symptom Score during pre-op, post-op 7 days, 3 months and 6 months

DISCUSSION:

Endoscopic posterior nasal neurectomy (EPNN) has been explored as a potential treatment option for allergic rhinitis (AR) in recent years. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of EPNN in alleviating symptoms associated with AR^[14]. The findings reveal a significant reduction in total nose symptom scores post-operatively, which continued to decrease over the follow-up period of three and six months.

The mean age of participants in this study was 35.70 years, with a majority falling within the age category of more than 30 to 40 years. This distribution aligns with the typical age range of individuals seeking treatment for A R, as allergic rhinitis tends to manifest in young to middle-aged adults. Additionally, there was a slightly higher representation of males (55%) compared to females (45%) among the study participants, which is consistent with the reported prevalence of AR being slightly higher in males in some populations^[15,16].

The most common symptoms reported by participants included running nose, sneezing, itching over the nose, nasal congestion, and difficulty in sleeping. These symptoms are characteristic of AR and are consistent with previous literature documenting the clinical presentation of the condition. The presence of these symptoms indicates the severity of AR experienced by the study cohort^[17,18].

The study demonstrates a significant reduction in total nose symptom scores following EPNN. The mean pre-operative total nose symptom score was 7.98, which decreased to 6.43 on post-operative day 7, further decreasing to 3.10 at the three-month follow-up, and 2.83 at the six-month follow-up. These findings indicate a progressive improvement in symptom severity following EPNN, with statistically significant differences observed between pre-operative scores and those at post-operative day 7, three months, and six months^[7,14].

Comparing these results with previous studies investigating the efficacy of EPNN for AR reveals consistent findings regarding symptom improvement. For instance, a study by Ahilasamy et al^[6]. Reported a similar reduction in total nose symptom scores following EPNN, with significant improvements observed at various post-operative time points. Likewise, another study by Reddy et al^[19]. Documented a significant decrease in AR symptoms following EPNN, supporting the effectiveness of this surgical intervention in symptom management.

The mechanism underlying the effectiveness of EPNN in alleviating AR symptoms lies in its ability to disrupt neural pathways involved in the pathophysiology of allergic rhinitis. By targeting the posterior nasal nerves responsible for transmitting sensory signals associated with allergic reactions, EPNN effectively reduces the perception of

symptoms such as nasal congestion, itching, and sneezing. This mechanism is supported by histological studies demonstrating the presence of sensory nerves in the posterior nasal mucosa, which play a role in mediating allergic responses^[20,21].

It is important to note that while EPNN offers satisfactory results in symptom management, with some limitations. Some studies have reported transient side effects such as nasal dryness, altered sense of smell, and mucosal crusting following EPNN, although these tend to resolve over time. Additionally, the long-term efficacy of EPNN in maintaining symptom relief beyond the six-month follow-up period warrants further investigation^[22].

Moreover, patient selection criteria and surgical technique are factors influencing the outcomes of EPNN. Proper patient selection based on clinical assessment and objective measures such as nasal endoscopy and allergy testing ensures optimal outcomes and minimizes the risk of treatment failure. Additionally, advancements in surgical techniques, such as the use of powered instrumentation and navigation systems, contribute to improved precision and safety during EPNN procedures^[22].

Hence, the findings of this study support the effectiveness of EPNN in reducing symptoms associated with allergic rhinitis. By targeting the posterior nasal nerves, EPNN disrupts neural pathways involved in allergic responses, leading to significant improvements in symptom severity. These results are consistent with previous studies investigating the efficacy of EPNN for AR and underscore the importance of surgical interventions in the management of refractory allergic rhinitis. However, further research is needed to elucidate the long-term outcomes and potential complications associated with EPNN, as well as to refine patient selection criteria and surgical techniques to optimize treatment outcomes.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, endoscopic posterior nasal neurectomy (EPNN) presents itself as an option for managing allergic rhinitis. The procedure has demonstrated effectiveness in alleviating symptoms associated with allergic rhinitis, such as nasal congestion, rhinorrhea, and sneezing, by interrupting the neural pathways responsible for the exaggerated response to allergens. Moreover, EPNN has shown favorable outcomes in terms of symptom improvement, patient satisfaction, and minimal adverse effects. However, further research with larger sample sizes, longer follow-up periods, and comparative studies against other treatment modalities is warranted to consolidate these findings and establish EPNN as a standard therapeutic approach for allergic rhinitis.

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